

GENERALIZED EXPERT OPINION BASED ON FUZZY NUMBER

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ABSTRACT

Fuzzy logic is a mathematical discipline that brings structure to the way we use and interpret our behavior in our daily lives. We see concepts of fuzzy logic in many places of our life. Fuzzy logic is particularly useful in highly complex systems that are difficult to understand and interpret, and in processes that rely on human thought, perception, or decision-making. Fuzzy theory, which is the basis of fuzzy logic, is a mathematical expression of fuzzy concepts. Another innovation in fuzzy theory is the nature of the information used. Fuzzy theory uses perceptual knowledge rather than measurement-based knowledge. But probability theory cannot process perceptual information. Because there is no mechanism to show and take into account the meaning of perceptions in probability theory. On the other hand, in fuzzy theory, it is possible to calculate with words instead of numbers. With fuzzy theory, phenomena can be made more realistic and explained with verbal variables.

Despite the wide application of many methods of fuzzy logic, especially in the field of fuzzy decision-making, it seems very important to talk about the decision-making technique without relation to the reliability and validity of the analyzed information. tends to be useless or even harmful. In this case, Z-scores have significant potential to describe the uncertainty of human knowledge, since both expert judgment and the Z-score involve limitations and reliability of the measured value. Therefore, the article proposes a method of converting expert opinion into Z number and presents a new aggregation approach.

Keywords: fuzzy logic, Z number, triangular fuzzy numbers, trapezoidal fuzzy numbers, expert opinion.

ENTRY

The real world is complex, and this complexity stems from uncertainty and generally imprecise decision making. Uncertainties are always present in many social, economic and technical matters due to the immaturity of human thinking. Human-made computers cannot handle such uncertainties, and computers require numerical information to function. Since it is impossible to fully understand a real event due to the inadequacy of human knowledge, the human thinking system and mind have the ability to think about such events and process information that contains incompleteness or uncertainty. In general, sources of information such as complexity and uncertainty occurring in various forms are called fuzzy sources. The thinking and decision-making mechanism that allows making consistent and correct decisions based on such complete and inaccurate information is called fuzzy logic (Allahverdi, 2002: 157).

Fuzzy logic enables the inclusion of verbal ambiguities in everyday speech during modeling and computation. In reality, human judgments are imprecise and fuzzy, and unfit to be expressed in precise numerical values. Therefore, it would be more realistic to use verbal variables in modeling human decisions. An important difference of fuzzy logic from other logic systems is that it allows the use of verbal variables (Li and Yang, 2004: 264).

Another feature that distinguishes fuzzy logic from other logic systems is that two properties called the third principle of inconsistency and the principle of contradiction, which are very important to other logic systems and can even be called fundamental rules, cannot be valid for fuzzy logic. In fuzzy logic, it cannot

be said that a proposition cannot be both true and false at the same time. This situation comes from the fact that the truth is very valuable and the meaning attributed to the conjunctions "and" in this context (Baykal and Beyan, 2004a: 39).

PURPOSE

The purpose of the study is to provide brief information about fuzzy logic, to create a graphic representation of the types of fuzzy numbers, to reveal the essence of the number Z.

RELEVANCE OF THE PROBLEM AND RELATED RESEARCH

The field of application of fuzzy logic is very wide, and it is possible to provide economic control using these fields of application. The relevance of the research lies in the development of new algorithms and software that can help people make decisions under mixed uncertainty with multiple parameters and imprecisely defined factors.

METHODS

Several methods were used in the article. First of all, data were collected using logical, analysis and synthesis methods, and then they were combined in the order required for the purposes of the study. In this work, we present a study that aims to find the most efficient ways to handle them (such as merge, add, divide). First, it is necessary to identify all available methods for collecting Z numbers. Second, it is necessary to discover new ways of working with them. Thirdly, the most interesting techniques should be investigated in detail and summarized. There is also a program designed to model the real word task of decision making.

The more one learns about a system, the better it can be understood and the less complexity one can create about it, but it does not disappear completely. The more complex the systems under study, or the less information available, the more effective the fuzziness will be. In the search for solutions for these systems, it is possible to arrive at a meaningful and useful solution by using fuzzy logic rules from fuzzy input and output data.

Fuzzy logic is used in two senses. In the narrow sense, fuzzy logic is a generalized form of classical bivalent logic. Broadly speaking, it refers to all theories and technologies that use fuzzy sets. Narrow fuzzy logic is a branch of broad fuzzy logic. Other fields; fuzzy control, fuzzy model definition, fuzzy arithmetic, fuzzy mathematical programming, fuzzy decision analysis, fuzzy neural networks. In all these areas, the traditional concept of black-white binary membership has been generalized to the concept of partial membership. Thus, human knowledge containing vague concepts is easier to explain and more effective solutions to real-life problems can be found (Yen and Langari, 1999: 3-4).

The concept of fuzzy logic was first introduced in 1965 by Lotfi A. Zadeh in his article "Fuzzy sets" published in "Information and Control" magazine. This article provides the definition, basic operations, concepts and properties of fuzzy sets. Zadeh (1965) stated that the closer one examines real-world problems, the more blurred the solution becomes. Because people cannot draw certain conclusions from all information sources simultaneously and interactively. It should be emphasized here that information sources include basic and accurate information, especially oral information. Since people can think verbally and communicate what they know to others through verbal expressions, these expressions cannot be expected to be accurate.

A key area to be evaluated by fuzzy systems is how such information would be considered for resolution if detected. Fuzzy logic tries to model any problem approximately and manage it with solutions that will not be mathematically complex (Baykal and Beyan,

2004a: 40). A fuzzy logic approach enables machines to process people's personal data and act on their experiences and intuitions. It uses symbolic expressions instead of numerical expressions when acquiring this ability. The transfer of these symbolic expressions to machines is based on mathematical foundations. This mathematical basis is fuzzy set theory and fuzzy logic (Elmas, 2003a: 25). Fuzzy logic makes it possible to control machines and products independently and more effectively through human-like process knowledge. Fuzzy logic uses expert estimates or approaches and has the ability to include subjective or fuzzy concepts such as fast, wide, little or blue, along with green (Erturul, 1996: 4). In other words; Since fuzzy logic deals with the degree of truth or falsity, it can also be regarded as a rather extended variant of two-level logic. So much so that the spectrum between right and wrong has been expanded by including the concepts of partially right and partially wrong (Erturul, 1996: 6).

The human brain's ability to think is different from that of computers. When judging, computers follow specific steps based on black or white statements and use the 0 – 1 system. And people make judgments based on their own judgments with expressions that contain uncertainty and ambiguity. Fuzzy or gray states take values between 0 and 1. While the human brain works easily with these fuzzy models, the same is not true for computers. With the help of fuzzy logic, this deficiency is tried to be eliminated (Kosko, 1997: 3-4). But what fuzzy logic can do is limited. Fuzzy logic cannot fully imitate human thought and creativity. However, fuzzy logic is predefined for the same situations, creating a solution for the situation.

A **fuzzy number** is a convex and normalized fuzzy set defined in $\mathbb{R}$ and having a piecewise continuous membership function. In other words, a fuzzy number represents an interval of exact numbers with a fuzzy boundary. A classic example of a fuzzy number is a triangular fuzzy number. It is represented by the set of two boundary points a_1 a_3 and a peak point a_2 , i.e. $[a_1, a_2, a_3]$, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1

In 2010, the concept of Z-scores was proposed, which is associated with the reliability factor of information for decision-making tasks, the description of various aspects of the world, and the expression of ideas or evaluations.

A number Z is an ordered pair of fuzzy numbers denoted as $Z = (A, R)$. The first component A with a constraint on values is the real-valued indefinite variable X . The second component R is a measure of reliability for the first component.

$Z +$ units. A $Z +$ number is a combination of fuzzy numbers. Written as $Z + = (A, R)$, A plays the same role as the number Z , where R is the probability distribution of a random number.

Fuzzy numbers are a special subset of fuzzy sets. About 5, almost 9, about 15, less than 200, etc. Fuzzy numbers are very useful for characterizing imprecise or approximate numerical quantities (Özkan, 2003: 59). It is possible to use different fuzzy numbers according to the topic under discussion. There are two fuzzy numbers commonly used in practical applications, triangular and trapezoidal (Baykal and Beyan, 2004a: 234).

Triangular fuzzy numbers are a special type of fuzzy numbers defined by three real numbers. It is expressed as (a_1, a_2, a_3) . The parameters a_1, a_2 , and a_3 indicate the smallest possible value, the most likely value, and the largest possible value, respectively. An illustration of a triangular fuzzy number A is given in Figure 2 (Kahraman et al, 2004: 174).

Figure 2. Triangular fuzzy number

a_1 and a_3 are the lower and upper bound values of the fuzzy set support and the membership function of the triangular fuzzy number, where a_2 is an integer odd number:

$$\mu(x/M) = \begin{cases} 0, & x < a_1, \\ (x - a_1) / (a_2 - a_1), & a_1 \leq x \leq a_2, \\ (a_3 - x) / (a_3 - a_2), & a_2 \leq x \leq a_3, \\ 0, & x > a_3 \end{cases}$$

Some features to consider when working with triangular fuzzy numbers can be listed as follows:

- The result of adding and subtracting two triangular fuzzy numbers is again a triangular fuzzy number.
- Multiplication, division, and inverse operations on triangular fuzzy numbers do not always result in triangular fuzzy numbers.
- Maximum or minimum operations on triangular fuzzy numbers do not always result in triangular fuzzy numbers.

Trapezoidal fuzzy numbers are one of the most commonly used fuzzy numbers. Among the reasons for frequent use of trapezoidal fuzzy numbers is that triangular fuzzy numbers are a special form of trapezoidal fuzzy numbers and they are easily understood by verbal variables (Baykal and Beyan, 2004a: 239).

Figure 3. Trapezoidal fuzzy numbers

A trapezoidal fuzzy number is defined by four parameters. A_1 and a_4 are the lower and upper bound values of the fuzzy set support, and a_2 and a_3 are the membership functions representing the bounds of the set of full membership numbers:

$$\mu A(x) = \begin{cases} 0, & x < a_1 \\ (x - a_1) / (a_2 - a_1), & a_1 \leq x \leq a_2 \\ 1, & a_2 \leq x \leq a_3 \\ (x - a_4) / (a_3 - a_4), & a_3 \leq x \leq a_4 \\ 0, & x > a_4 \end{cases}$$

Some examples of daily expert assessments can be explained as follows:

1. "What is the weather forecast for tomorrow?" I really don't know, but I'm sure the weather will be hot." In this example, during the conversation, the expert presents a hypothesis about the expected weather from a linguistic point of view and indicates the degree of confidence in it. So $X = \text{Weather forecast for tomorrow}$ and $Z = \text{warm, sure} >$.

2. "It takes me about 2 weeks to finish the course work." So $X = \text{Time to complete Coursework}$ and $Z = \text{about 2 weeks} >$.

The degree of validity or reliability of expert assessment can be presented in two ways, i.e. in an overt or implicit form. The overt form is reflected in the linguistic term "absolutely sure" in the first example, and the hidden form in the context in the second example.

The proposed method of converting expert opinion into a Z number involves describing a strict form that an expert must fill out to provide knowledge. Each expert expresses his opinion by filling out the form with a question written in the developed form. The form should have N sections with $\mathcal{A}$. Each section should contain several questions describing the relation of the criterion $C \in \mathcal{A}$ to the object $O \in \mathcal{Q}$. The first and fourth questions are related to the principal part of the Z-score, and the other questions are some kind of reliability measure for the first component. Based on expert opinion, according to C , it is necessary to collect various Z-numbers into one Z-number, which can describe the entire relationship of O with the subject. There are at least three methods of collection:

1. Convert the number Z to a simple fuzzy number and add using simple methods
2. Summing up parts A and B separately
3. Convert Z to $Z +$, add the $Z +$ numbers, and then convert the given $Z +$ to Z

CONCLUSION

Fuzzy logic approach has some advantages and disadvantages compared to classical approaches. The advantages of fuzzy logic concept can be listed as follows:

- The most important advantages of fuzzy logic are that it is close to human thinking, adapts to mathematical models, is fast and cheap to apply, shapes human behavior and is open to new possibilities.

- Because the fuzzy logic approach does not need a mathematical model, time-varying and non-linear systems where the mathematical model is not well defined are the most successful application areas.

- It is more flexible and safer than classical mathematical modeling for real-life problems because it is applicable in situations involving human factor, uncertainty, personal bias, behavior and goals.

Fuzzy logic has some advantages as well as some disadvantages. Some of these disadvantages can be mentioned as follows:

- In fuzzy logic applications, rules should be defined based on expert experience. Defining membership functions and fuzzy logic rules is not always easy.

- There is no specific method and learning ability that gives certain results in determining membership functions. The most convenient method is trial and error, which can take a very long time. It is very difficult to estimate how many membership functions are really needed without extensive testing.

- The main problem of fuzzy logic is the lack of a proven method for analyzing stability, observability and controllability of systems. Today, this is possible only with expensive experiments (Elmas, 2003a: 39-40).

- The lack of a specific formal design and lack of good measurements, compared to traditional methods, can be counted among its disadvantages, the inability to predict how well it will work and when to use it.

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